

GPM2220000811: peptide model: 18030.1.1 of ENSMUSP0000064155

ENSMUSP0000064155: Rif1.p, no protein text annotation available

Sample information

#	log(e)	log(l)	m+h	delta	ζ	sequence
18030	-6.5	4.00	2257.0382	0.0004	2/3	yqtr ¹⁵³³ RASQGLISAVENSESDSSEA ¹⁵⁵³ eevs (1337) 0.0012

mods: R1533+Label:+6 Da, S1535+Phospho, K1553+Label:+6 Da

CGItemp33452 scan 18030 (charge 2)

R A S Q G L I S A V E N S E S D S S E A K

matched/total: # ions: 66% intensity: 38% μ: -0.02, σ: 0.04 Da

bond	+1 _y	+1 _y -17	+1 _y -18	+1 _b	+1 _b -17	+1 _b -18
R ₁	2094.917	2077.890	2076.906	163.129	146.102	145.118
A ₂	2023.880	2006.853	2005.869	234.166	217.139	216.155
S ₃	1856.882	1839.855	1838.871	401.164	384.137	383.153
Q ₄	1728.823	1711.796	1710.812	529.223	512.196	511.212
G ₅	1671.801	1654.775	1653.791	586.244	569.217	568.233
L ₆	1558.717	1541.691	1540.707	699.328	682.302	681.318
I ₇	1445.633	1428.607	1427.623	812.412	795.386	794.402
S ₈	1358.601	1341.575	1340.591	899.444	882.418	881.434
A ₉	1287.564	1270.538	1269.554	970.481	953.455	952.471
V ₁₀	1188.496	1171.469	1170.485	1069.550	1052.523	1051.539
E ₁₁	1059.453	1042.427	1041.443	1198.592	1181.566	1180.582
N ₁₂	945.410	928.384	927.400	1312.635	1295.609	1294.625
S ₁₃	858.378	841.352	840.368	1399.667	1382.641	1381.657
E ₁₄	729.336	712.309	711.325	1528.710	1511.683	1510.699
S ₁₅	642.304	625.277	624.293	1615.742	1598.715	1597.731
D ₁₆	527.277	510.250	509.266	1730.769	1713.742	1712.758
S ₁₇	440.245	423.218	422.234	1817.801	1800.774	1799.790
S ₁₈	353.213	336.186	335.202	1904.833	1887.806	1886.822
E ₁₉	224.170	207.143	206.159	2033.875	2016.849	2015.865
A ₂₀	153.133	136.106	135.122	2104.913	2087.886	2086.902

Other observed ions:

ion type	m/z	ion type	m/z
b[6]-H ₃ PO ₄	601.328	ay[6-12]	699.404
b[7]-H ₃ PO ₄	714.412	ay[14-21]	812.373
by[12-21]	1041.443	a[10]	1041.550
ay[5-15]	1059.532	by[10-19]	1064.401
by[8-18]	1093.428	ay[4-14]	1100.558
b[11]-H ₃ PO ₄	1100.592	(parent-2H ₂ O) ⁺²	1111.012
(parent-2NH ₃) ⁺²	1111.996	(parent-H ₂ O) ⁺²	1120.017
ay[9-21]	1312.596	b[14]-H ₃ PO ₄	1430.710
ay[4-18]	1476.681	b[16]-H ₃ PO ₄	1632.769

Residue modification sets tested:

Complete mods: i. Carbamidomethyl@C, Label:+6 Da@K, Label:+6 Da@R

Protein-specific PTMs: i. Phospho@S, Phospho@Y, Phospho@T, Acetyl@K
N-terminal: i. Ammonia-loss@Q, Ammonia-loss@C, Dehydrated@E (peptide)
 ii. ragged, Acetyl (protein)

E-value calculation:

$\log(E) = 5.047 + -0.226 x$

x	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22*	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
log(n)	4.05	4.05	4.04	3.98	3.89	3.75	3.61	3.49	3.27	3.04	2.87	2.67	2.47	2.31	1.95	1.20	-	1.43	1.08	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.15
x	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53							
log(n)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.85	-						

Peptide found in the following 3 proteins:

1. [ENSMUSP00000108313](#) [Rif1:p](#), replication timing regulatory factor 1 [Source:MGI Symbol;Acc:[MGI:1098622](#)]
[IPR016024](#) ARM repeat
[IPR028566](#) ($\times 2$) TELOMERE-ASSOCIATED PROTEIN RIF1
[IPR022031](#) Rif1 N

2. [ENSMUSP00000064155](#) [Rif1:p](#), no protein text annotation available

3. [ENSMUSP00000108312](#) [Rif1:p](#), no protein text annotation available

Contributor: anonymous

store trace yes